

significantly. Plots treated with 75-50-50 kg NPK + azolla yielded as well as those with 100-50-50 kg NPK alone (5.2 vs 5.4 t/ha), indicating that azolla might supplement 25 kg N/ha. The yield from 0-50-50 kg NPK + azolla (4.4 t/ha) was similar to that from

25-50-50 kg NPK/ha (4.6 t/ha).

A similar investigation was undertaken at the Ambasamudram Paddy Experiment Station in the 1978-79 kar season with the rice variety ADT31. The results show that the incorporation of azolla along with 50 kg N/ha gave yields equal

to those with 75 kg N/ha alone (5.9 t/ha) indicating a saving of 25 kg N/ha. Azolla incorporation with 100 kg N/ha was superior to 100 kg N/ha alone (6.5 vs 6.3 t/ha). The results clearly indicated the positive effect of azolla inoculation in increasing grain yield. ■

Field conditions suitable for blue-green algae multiplication

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To determine the optimal field conditions for growth of blue-green algae, a trial was conducted in March 1979 in a field rich in the algae. Six conditions (see table) were tried with four replications. In the 10-m² bundled plots of the experiment, water height was maintained at 5 cm. Superphosphate was applied to the plots at 160 kg P₂O₅/ha. To control pests on the algae, 250 g carbofuran 3% G was applied to each plot. Seedlings of ADT31 were used for the planted field treatment.

Blue-green algae^a yields. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Yield (kg/10 m ²)	Blue-green algae types in descending order of abundance
With fresh stubbles	5.84	M1, Ad, Pb
With stubbles up to soil surface	5.68	M1, Ad, Pb
Stubbles removed	3.96	M1, Ad, Pb
Stubbles incorporated	4.43	M1, Ad
Plowed, prepared without stubbles	3.16	M1, Ad
Planted field	6.23	M1, Ad
CD	0.36	

^a M1 = *Microcoleus lacustris*, Ad = *Anabaena doliolum*, Pb = *Plectonema boryanum*.

Twenty days after the treatments began, blue-green algae floating on the water surface were collected, dried, and weighed.

Blue-green algae multiplication was highest in the planted field (see table).

In the first three treatments, three types of blue-green algae – *Microcoleus lacustris*, *Anabaena doliolum*, and *Plectonema boryanum* – were observed. In the others, *P. boryanum* was not found. ■

Environment and its influence

Effect of air temperature on rice flower temperature

I. Nishiyama, visiting scientist from the Tropical Agriculture Research Center, Japan (currently assigned to the Plant Physiology Department, International Rice Research Institute)

The temperature inside rice flowers was measured at different air temperatures on days of fine weather under flooding in phytotron glasshouse rooms, growth cabinets, screenhouses, and fields at IRRI and at the Regional Rice Research Station, Punjab Agricultural University, Kapurthala, Punjab, India.

When ambient air temperature was lower than 30°C, the temperature inside the flower was slightly higher (see figure). When it was higher than 30°C, the temperature inside the flower was lower. The difference increased with rising

Difference between temp inside and near flower (°C)

Effect of air temperature on flower temperature in the rice plant.

temperature, reaching about 2°C at the ambient air temperature of 40°C.

Studies on leaf temperature in other species have yielded the following information:

- Leaf temperature is affected by solar radiation, ambient air temperature, air and soil moisture, and wind velocity.
- Leaf temperature is higher than ambient air temperature with high light intensity, without moisture stress and at lower temperatures. The difference decreases with rising temperature, and leaf temperature becomes lower than that of ambient air above a given temperature (changing point).
- The changing point depends on species and environmental factors, but it tends to be about 33°C under high light intensity without water stress.
- Leaf transpiration causes lowering of leaf temperature at higher air

Effect of air humidity on difference between inside and ambient temperatures of the rice flower (artificially lit growth cabinet). IRRI, 1979.

Vapor pressure deficit (mb)	Relative humidity (%)	Temperature (°C)		
		Inside flower	Near flower	Difference
12	79	33.1	33.9	-0.8
24	57	33.0	33.9	-0.9
36	36	32.6	34.5	-1.9

temperature.

The figure shows that the same mechanism regulates temperature in rice flowers and in the leaves of other plant species. Furthermore it indicates that transpiration has the same order in the rice flowers and in the leaves.

Air humidity affects the temperature of the rice flower through transpiration (see table). Wind also affects it in some ways. Nevertheless, the figure provides a rough estimate of flower temperature in flooded fields on fine days.

The data will be useful in studies on

sterility induced by high temperature at anthesis. Such sterility is the most serious damage caused by high temperature in the rice plant. The sensitive period is just before and during flower opening, and thus the sterility should be attributed to the temperature inside the flower at that time. Although estimation of flower temperature is not easy and has not been done, these data can be used for approximate estimation of the flower temperature from the air temperature around the flower. ■

Announcements

International rice workshop-monitoring tour in China

Thirty rice researchers from 8 countries recently participated in a 10-day international workshop and monitoring tour in the People's Republic of China.

The workshop-monitoring tour, the first to be held in China, was jointly sponsored by the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences (CAAS) and IRRI. Its major purpose was to encourage cooperation through the International Rice Testing Program (IRTP).

From 22 to 26 October, the group met at the Guangzhou (formerly Canton) branch of CAAS. Papers were presented and collaborative rice research progress was discussed. Emphasis was on breeding to develop varieties with genetic resistance to insects and diseases, and on cultural practices to enable farmers to control pests without costly chemicals. The participants also visited rice-growing

communes and rice research centers in southern China.

On 27 October the participants traveled by train to Ch'angsha, central China, where they observed research sites, communes, and the Hunan province branch of CAAS. They also saw part of the more than 5 million ha of hybrid rice now being grown in China.

The IRTP is a worldwide network coordinated by IRRI and financed by a grant from the United Nations Development Programme. Scientists from across the rice-growing world enter their best rice varieties in the IRTP. Seeds of these elite rices are sent to IRRI, which distributes them to peer scientists in about 75 nations for uniform testing under diverse environmental conditions. National scientists release the best IRTP lines to farmers under local names, or cross them with local varieties.

Participants from outside China were: N. C. Brady, IRRI director general;

M. R. Vega, IRRI deputy director general; H. E. Kauffman, IRTP joint coordinator; D. V. Seshu, IRTP joint coordinator; Semsak Awakul, assistant director, Rice Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok 9, Thailand; T. T. Chang, IRRI geneticist; Irwin Gunawardena, botanist, Central Agricultural Research Institute, Peradeniya, Sri Lanka; T. R. Hargrove, IRRI editor; E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI entomologist; M. B. Kalode, entomologist, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), Hyderabad, India; G. S. Khush, IRRI plant breeder; K. C. Ling, IRRI plant pathologist; I. N. Oka, entomologist, Central Research Institute for Agriculture (CRIA), Bogor, Indonesia; H. K. Pande, director, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India; R. Seetharaman, director, AICRIP; B. H. Siwi, rice program leader, CRIA; S. M. H. Zaman, director, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Bangladesh. ■